

PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FEATURES OF DEVELOPING SOCIAL- EMOTIONAL-CIVIC COMPETENCE IN MOTHER LANGUAGE LESSONS

Arabboyeva Mahfuzakhon Akramjonovna
Doctoral student of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15036886>

Annotation: The article covers the pedagogical-psychological and methodological aspects of developing social-emotional-civic competencies in 6th-7th grade students through mother tongue education, the role of mother tongue education in human life, and the specific aspects of developing students' basic and subject-specific competencies in the process of mother tongue education.

Key words and concepts: social-emotional-civic competence, components of social-emotional-civic competence, psychological impact, psychological characteristics, pedagogical characteristics, methodological characteristics.

In order for our country to become one of the most powerful leading countries in the international arena, it is necessary to pay special attention to school education, enrich programs and textbooks in all subjects with completely new content and forms that will make our current lifestyle more prosperous, especially to find ways to radically improve the quality and effectiveness of native language education, and to ensure that all pedagogical personnel working in our country, including native language and literature teachers, constantly work on themselves and organize educational processes in accordance with world standards. They must systematically study the causes and factors of growth and development in education in countries around the world and organize lessons based on the knowledge they have acquired, set themselves the goal of forming and developing basic and subject-related competencies in students, and educate the student personality in accordance with the requirements of the world, the state, and today's society. Because the mother tongue is the main criterion, the greatest wealth, which shows the existence of a nation on earth, serves as the basis for determining the unique prestige of a nation among all the nations and states in the world, and determines the longevity of a nation. Therefore, it is our duty to pay special attention to the teaching of the mother tongue in school education.

The market economy does not need a person with knowledge determined by a program, but an intelligent citizen who has mastered the ways of acquiring knowledge and has the ability to independently perceive in specific conditions.

Each subject is of particular importance in human life, each of them provides important knowledge for a person's well-being. However, the study of each subject, all knowledge in the world, and its transmission to future generations cannot be imagined without language. Linguistic and speech competencies acquired through the subject of the native language serve as the basis for the formation and development of all basic competencies, as well as for the acquisition of the necessary knowledge by independently mastering information and data from all other subjects. Because a person acquires knowledge about any subject by reading, listening, writing, and expressing it in speech. That is why the role of the subject of the native language in human life is incomparable.

High levels of educational effectiveness can only be achieved by providing quality information and educational processes that enable all students to acquire relevant knowledge, skills, and competencies.

The organization of educational processes based on a competency-based approach leads to the definition of the methodology for the formation of basic competencies and is aimed at directing the content of education to achieve results that are important for everyday life. The goal of today's education is to organize the educational process as a practical activity of the student, to form a set of certain knowledge, skills, competencies and semantic relations and personal characteristics in the student's personality through the prism of daily and professional activities of a person.

UNESCO's Incheon Declaration, which is planned for 2030, recognizes that "Education is the main driving force for development and a key activity leading to the Sustainable Development Goals". On this basis, systematic work is being carried out in the education systems of countries such as the USA, France, Russia, Germany, and England to develop a person's socio-emotional and civic competencies.

Social-emotional-civic competence is the ability of a person to realize himself and have a real opportunity to occupy a prestigious position in society, both socially and materially, and, undoubtedly, the formation and development of this competence in students is one of the most important tasks assigned to the education and upbringing system.

As pedagogical features of the development of socio-emotional-civic competence through native language education, we can say the following:

1. Determining the purpose of the lesson (which component of the competence is aimed at being formed or developed)
2. Organizing a lesson based on innovations and research in the field of new content of education.
3. Studying pedagogical technologies, methods and techniques that form a competence or its component.
4. Correctly choosing pedagogical technologies, methods and techniques that form a competence or its component.
5. Organizing learning through the performance of social roles that require the components of the competence or competence that is intended to be formed in the lesson process.
6. Organizing lesson processes based on the principle of collaborative work.
7. Conducting lessons by dividing them into groups and achieving teamwork among students.
8. Creating an environment for communication and interaction.
9. To create a culture of communication by creating a situation that forces the active use of linguistic and speech competencies in each lesson using the technologies and methods selected to achieve the educational goal, and thereby create an opportunity to achieve a socially active culture of communication.
10. To achieve the analysis of texts in the textbook on various topics together with teammates under the guidance of the teacher.

Our psychologists indicate the period from 10 to 15 years of age as a person's adolescence. It can be seen from this that a person's adolescence begins in the 5th-6th grade and is an important period when a student strives to be active as a part of society or when

education, family, and neighborhood take all measures to make him an active citizen in society. Taking this into account, first of all, special attention should be paid to this in the process of all subject lessons, especially in the teaching of the native language.

D.I. Feldstein explains the features of adolescence as follows: "... adolescence is an important moment of social development and is of particular importance in the formation of personality. The rapid development and saturation of the child's social position "I and society" is ensured by activities that are useful to society, because in this the teenager has the opportunity not only to attract attention, express himself, but also to see his "I". When evaluating other people, he feels that society recognizes him. This is a mechanism for developing the teenager's social position in relation to society, which serves as a starting point, a necessary internal condition for the further development of his activity as a form of self-expression, consciousness, self-awareness, personal identity, self-determination. This period is the most important moment for the inclusion of a person in social action, introducing him to the social movement of society. The externally imposed, pedagogically "imposed" demand on a teenager, recognized by society and approved by society, useful activity for society, forms a sphere of motivational needs that corresponds to him, because, on the one hand, it satisfies the expectations of the growing individual, his potential, and on the other hand, it forms the norms of his life activity, provides the practice of developing self-awareness".

Among adolescents, there is a noticeable imbalance in social ideals and values. This is characterized by the predominance of material values over spiritual values. Therefore, adolescents have a false idea of such qualities as kindness, justice, generosity, patriotism, and citizenship. At the same time, a low level of spirituality is observed among adolescents. This leads to neuropsychiatric disorders and suicide in children. To prevent these situations, it is important to form students' socio-emotional-civic competencies in the process of native language education by teaching them to critically respond to various situational problems using the word and its effects.

The process of socialization of adolescents and the formation of socio-emotional-civic competencies should be given a systematic, pedagogically controlled character.

Professor Y.A. Kustov shares his views on the league: "...if all educators, families and the public are involved in this important process, the socialization crisis of new generations can be prevented".

The study of scientific and pedagogical literature shows that a systematic approach to the process of socialization and upbringing of the younger generation should be based on a specific educational model.

In the process of forming socio-emotional-civic competence in 6-7th grade students through native language education, special attention should be paid to taking into account the age-related psychological characteristics of students, creating a favorable educational environment, forming a favorable psychological climate in the classroom, respectfully listening to and accepting each of his ideas within the framework of the specified topic by the teacher and students, regardless of their content level and quality, not discussing his ideas critically, avoiding critical and personally derogatory verbal influence on students by the teacher and using persuasive methods to the maximum extent, and organizing a process that does not allow situations that cause stress in students. When a student feels free during the lesson, feels respect and trust from his classmates, he tries to think to a certain extent, is not

afraid to express any opinion, and when he feels that his thoughts are supported, he tries to give more beautiful thoughts, which gradually ensures that the student becomes active in cooperation with his teammates.

In modern conditions, socio-economic changes in the world require education not only to provide a certain level of knowledge, skills and qualifications in the basics of science, but also to provide the ability to live in society, interact with members of society and successfully solve life problems, achieve socially significant goals, and effectively work. Because the school performs the most important task in the socialization of the child, and therefore it is the responsibility of education to prepare a person for social life. In the implementation of this task and goal, along with all subjects, the role of mother tongue education is of particular importance. Since communication plays a central role in human socialization, the ability of a person to think independently and creatively is realized in the process of forming linguistic and speech competencies in the subject in native language lessons.

In the current era, socio-economic changes mean that the task of education is not only to provide students with knowledge, to form students' skills and competencies based on the knowledge they have acquired, but also to ensure their ability to effectively achieve socially important goals in modern conditions, to communicate freely with members of society, and to successfully solve life problems throughout their lives.

Every child in the world needs a balanced set of cognitive and social-emotional-civic skills to live a fulfilling life. Schools are the primary developmental context for children and adolescents and play a central role in the development of students' important life skills, including social-emotional-civic competencies.

In order to develop social-emotional-civic competencies in the educational process, it is necessary to know all its components and understand which components to develop in which lesson or with which content.

The components of social-emotional-civic competence are:

- Adaptability
- Problem recognition
- Reactivity (emotional)
- Strong self-confidence
- Emotional management
- Influencing others
- Achieving success
- Empathy
- Emotional recognition
- Working with others
- Achieving goals
- Leadership
- Self-management
- Perseverance
- Respect for oneself and others
- Responsibility
- Interpersonal culture
- Communication

From the above, it can be seen that through native language education, this competence is developed in the following areas: adaptability, problem recognition, reactivity, strong self-confidence, emotional management, influencing others, achieving success, empathy, emotional recognition, working with others, achieving goals, leadership, self-management, perseverance, respect for oneself and others, responsibility, interpersonal culture. We can develop all components such as culture, communication, and initiative.

Social engagement helps children develop initiative, self-management, self-confidence, and the ability to work with others.

The goal of developing foundational and science-related competencies in students is to acquire the ability to successfully live in a changing world and implement areas of sustainable development of society.

By organizing the education system based on a competency-based approach, we can achieve the following:

- ensuring sustainable personal development of students based on setting life goals, health and safety, self-development, and self-awareness;
- developing independent, systematic, critical, and creative thinking, which determines the effectiveness of solving problems associated with wide uncertainty in the modern world;
- developing emotional regulation competencies that provide recognition and management of emotions, empathy;
- forming communicative competencies that require mastering oral and written speech, the use of information and communication technologies, and the acquisition of constructive communication styles and methods;
- developing collaborative competencies through gaining and enriching experience in team building and leadership, cooperation, and creating and maintaining a favorable socio-psychological environment;
- to educate citizens through humanistic values, awareness of national identity, patriotism, and involvement in socially useful activities.

We believe that it is important to rely on the following principles in developing basic competencies in students.

- Orientation of educational goals to sustainable personal development and successful socialization;
- Including in the content of education in all academic subjects and academic subjects, along with subject-specific competencies, components of basic competencies and components related to universal competencies (critical and creative thinking, emotional regulation, communication, cooperation).
- Orientation of the studied academic subjects to human vital needs.

Person-centered education is important in the formation of basic and subject-specific competencies in the student.

A person-centered approach is implemented not only by organizing the educational process taking into account the needs of the individual, his motives, goals, interests, attitudes, needs, requirements, but also through the active position of the student. The process of self-knowledge, self-development and self-awareness. Compliance with a person-centered approach in the formation of students' basic and subject-specific competencies and the subjective participation of each student in the educational process are important in achieving the goal of education.

As the main psychological, pedagogical and methodological features of the development of students' socio-emotional and civic competencies, we can indicate the following:

1. Psychological and pedagogical features:

- age and individual characteristics of students (cognitive, emotional, social).
- the influence of the social environment, cultural traditions, family upbringing on the formation of students' values and attitudes.
- the role of learning activities, communication with peers and teachers in the development of socio-emotional skills.

2. Methodological features:

- the use of interactive teaching methods (discussions, role-playing games, practical situations).
- creating situations that encourage the expression of emotions, moral reasoning and civic positions.
- organizing group work that helps develop communication, leadership and team skills.
- introducing topics related to social responsibility, ethics and civic participation in training courses.
- conducting extracurricular activities (volunteering, social projects, discussion clubs).
- using portfolios and reflective assignments to help students understand their personal growth.
- collaboration of teachers with psychologists and social workers to comprehensively support the development of students.

In the process of forming socio-emotional-civic competencies, the following qualities and characteristics are formed in students.

- self-awareness (self-esteem, emotional management, motivation).
- social awareness (empathy, understanding others).
- responsible decision-making (solving problems, assessing the impact).
- interpersonal communication skills (cooperation, conflict resolution).
- civic activity (social responsibility, participation in public life).

The following can be said as the psychological and pedagogical tasks of developing educational competencies in grades 6 and 7:

- encouraging students' social activity in and out of school, mastering role models of activity and behavior, and directing them towards a profession;
- to help students form a body image of the "I", male and female identity, to understand their uniqueness;
- to create conditions for the formation of life goals and values;
- to expand time perspectives and opportunities;
- to stimulate the desire to independently solve problems, self-education, self-control and develop willpower;
- to promote the development of abstract thinking skills.

In conclusion, it can be said that a comprehensive approach to the development of socio-emotional-civic competence in native language education, which combines psychological, pedagogical and methodological aspects, allows creating conditions for the comprehensive development of students' social, emotional and civic competences.

Literature used in the article:

1. "O'zbekistonning yangi taraqqiyot davrida ta'lim-tarbiya va ilm-fan sohalarini rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 06.11.2020-yildagi PF-6108-son farmoni.
2. "2022 — 2026-yillarda xalq ta'limini rivojlantirish bo'yicha milliy dasturni tasdiqlash to'g'risida" 11.05.2022. PF-133-son farmoni.
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017-yil 6-apreldagi "Umumiy o'rta va o'rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta'limining davlat ta'lim standartlarini tasdiqlash to'g'risida" gi 187-son qarori.
4. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017-yil 6-apreldagi "Umumiy o'rta va o'rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta'limining davlat ta'lim standartlarini tasdiqlash to'g'risida" gi 187-son qarori asosida yaratilgan Ona tili fanidan o'quv dasturi (5-9-sinf)
5. Ona tili fani bo'yicha O'zbekiston Respublikasi Uzluksiz ta'lim milliy o'quv dasturlari. Ta'lim sifatini nazorat qilish davlat inspeksiyasi. Toshkent-2021.
6. Incheon declaration/ Education 2030: Towards inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all (Word Education Forum, 19-22 may 2015, Incheon, Republic of Korea).- Корея.-2015. 35-bet.
7. Образование 2030 Инчхонская декларация и рамочная программа действий.: Республики Корея с 19 по 25 мая 2015 г.
8. Фельдштейн, Д.И. Психология взросления: структурно-содержательные характеристики процесса развития личности: Избранные труды / Д.И. Фельдштейн. – М.: Московский психолого-социальный институт: Флинта, 2004. — 670 с.
9. Кустов, Ю.А. Социальная компетенция педагога: монография / Ю.А. Кустов, О.Ю. Щербакова, Е.М. Садыкова, В.А. Гусев. – Самара: Изд-во ФГОУ СПО «Самарский государственный колледж», 2010. – 235с.
10. Ismoilova N., Abdullayeva D. Ijtimoiy psixologiya. – T.: O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashriyoti. 2013, 60-bet.
11. Yuldasheva Dilorom Nigmatovna. O'zbek tilini o'qitish metodikasi (kognitiv-pragmatik yondashuv asosida). "Durdona" nashriyoti Buxoro – 2021, 10-bet
12. Махмудов Ю.Ф., Худойкулов Х.Ж., Холмирзаев Э.Ж., Холмирзаев З.Ж. Педагогика ва психология. – Т.: "DIZAYN-PRESS" МЧЖ нашриёти. 2011, 216-б.
13. Arabboyeva M.A. Ona tili darslari orqali o'quvchilarning ijtimoiy- emotsional-fuqarolik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish. Zamonauiy ta'lim / современное образование. 2022, 12-son. 43-47-betlar.
14. Arabboyeva M.A. Ona tili darslarini milliy dastur talablari asosida tashkil etish dolzarb pedagogik muammo sifatida. Scientific Bulletin of NamSU-Научный вестник НамГУ-NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi – 2023 -yil, 7-son.
15. Arabboyeva M.A. O'quvchilarda ijtimoiy-emotsional-fuqarolik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning psixologik-pedagogik xususiyatlari. Zamonauiy ta'lim / современное образование. 2024.№5(138), 47-52-betlar.
16. Arabboyeva M.A. O'quvchilarning ijtimoiy emotsional-fuqarolik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish. "Umumiy filologiyaning dolzarb masalalari" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari, Andijon. 2023-yil, 14-iyun, 137-142.

17. Arabboyeva M.A. Ona tili darslarida ijtimoiy emotsional – fuqarolik kompetentsiyalarini shakllantirishga qo'yiladigan didaktik talablar. Andijon davlat chet tillari instituti hamda –UNIVERSAL xalqaro ilmiy jurnali hamkorligida "Globallashuv jarayonida fan va ta'lim muammolari va yechimlari" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari. 2024-yil 5-iyun, 224-227.

